

Coastal and Nautical Tourism in 2040: Jobs, Skills, Training

Co-Design Foresight Workshop

February 2023

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Glossary

Abbreviation / Acronym	Meaning
AUTH/SJMC	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki/ School of Journalism and mass media
EASME	European Agency for SMEs
EC	European Commission
EMFF	European Maritime and Fisheries Fund
ENAT	European Network for Accessible Tourism
ETIS	European Tourism Indicators System
GA	Grant Agreement
GEJI	Global Environmental Journalism Initiative
IKO	International Kitesurf Organisation
PC	Project Coordinator
PO	Project Officer (EC)
PSB	Project Steering Board
QA	Quality Assurance
SUP	Stand Up Paddle
UAG	User Advisory Group
UC	Usage Cases
WPL	Work Package Leaders
WST	Water Sports Tourism

Co-Design Foresight Workshop

Coastal and Nautical Tourism in 2040: Jobs, Skills, Training

Executive Summary

This report is the product of a long discussion that started with the submission of NAUTILUS project back in 2018 and culminated with a Co-design workshop on the future of jobs, skills, and training in the context of coastal and nautical tourism. NAUTILUS consortium decided that the best idea to investigate the future of blue careers in coastal tourism was to involve key stakeholders in a co-design exercise.

The foresight workshop was designed to address one focal question: **How will Coastal & Nautical Tourism be in 2040 in regard to Jobs, Skills, and Training?**

The **objectives** of the workshop were to:

- Discuss challenges for innovation and competitiveness of the Coastal & nautical Tourism
- Explore changes in education and training curricula for highly skilled workforce in Coastal and Nautical Tourism
- Detect in a forward-looking methodology the new trends in the coastal and nautical tourism sector

Participants of the workshop included representatives from the European Commission, the NAUTILUS Consortium, the tourism industry, and training providers. The workshop provided an opportunity for dialogue and debate on the challenges of innovation and competitiveness of the Coastal & Nautical Tourism sector. Discussions focused on the trends that affect the sector, new services, the skills, and training that the sector needs and really provocative and innovative ideas on future start-ups in tourism.

In the following chapters you will find:

- A short introduction to provide some context on the issues of coastal tourism blue careers.
- A brief description of **what Foresight is**, what are megatrends and how scenarios are built and why (Chapter 2).
- **Chapter 3** provides a rather detailed description on the **implementation of the workshop**. The tools we used, the methodology, the exercises and the templates we used to facilitate the process.
- The **future scenarios** are all presented in **chapter 4**. We have developed 4 of them based on the impact assessment of trends and uncertainties using Dator's "Four Futures" (we will explain more on this in the scenarios chapter).
- Finally, **chapter 5**, presents **some visions of the future** through ideas for tourism start-ups as they were envisaged through the eyes of the participants to the event.

We hope this report will be a useful tool for facilitating productive discussion and designing policies to help coastal tourism in Europe reach its full potential and ensure sustainability.

We can't predict the future, but we can do our best to be ready for it.

1 Background & Context

What is the NAUTILUS Project

NAUTILUS (Education & Certification Framework for Blue Career in Water Sports Tourism), is a 36-month, EU-funded project (GA: 863524) implemented under the [EMFF-Blue Economy-2018 call - Blue Careers]. The project started on November 2019 and concluded in January 2023 (with a 3-month extension).

The Nautilus Project, named after the ancient Nautilus Shell, a symbol of renewal, development, and expansion, proposes a university-business collaboration in the SE Mediterranean basin to extend knowledge and update education and training curriculum models for blue growth and sustainability.

- Nautilus vision was to **develop highly skilled and educated water sports tourism professionals** who could provide excellent services, act as local ambassadors, and raise awareness about the preservation of the seas and oceans.
- Our mission was to **create an innovative methodology for flexible, collaborative, work-based learning** that would offer learners the opportunity to gain basic theoretical knowledge and acquire new skills and competences.
- Nautilus aimed to broaden the scope of formal and informal education by bringing together a university, three water sports tourism SMEs, an IT company, and an accreditation and certification organization to collaborate and develop a training and professional qualification framework for up-skilling water sports tourism professionals.
- Our ambition was to **create attractive jobs in water sports tourism** without harming the marine environment and create new opportunities for a young generation that is, and wants to remain, close to the sea.

Our plan was to:

- **Map the educational and training offer & analyse the training/ learning needs** of the WST professionals, the industry skills needs and finally create their occupational profile.
- **Develop the methodology** and **deploy the tools and learning content** for an effective and innovative training experience.
- **Test the system in real life conditions** and create the first cohort of qualified and certified Water Sports Tourism professionals.

We broadly define **Water Sports Tourism** as any sports activity undertaken by a tourist in relation to water resources, such as lakes, canals, creeks, streams, rivers, waterways, coastal zones, seas, oceans. In NAUTILUS we dealt with non-motorised adventure sports like windsurfing, kitesurfing, surfing, stand up paddling (SUP), canoeing & kayaking etc. Nevertheless, our focus is not on the technical aspects of each one of these sports but in the hospitality, sustainability and soft skills that a professional instructor working in the tourism business should possess. At the same time, we promote safety and inclusiveness through emphasis on Water Safety Risk Management (WSRM) a combination of lifeguarding, first aid, emergency response, self-survival. All our results (including most training modules) can be easily adapted in other water related activities as well (scuba diving and even motorized water sports).

What are the results of the project?

- A **Water Sports Tourism Education Stakeholder Map** cataloguing and evaluating existing academic and VET institutions and their programmes in Water Sports and Tourism.
- A **profile of the Water Sports Tourism professionals** outlining what is needed by the industry and the best pathway for a young professional, including work opportunities and prospects.
- A **Learning Needs Analysis** to bridge the gap between the training offer and the industry needs.
- A **Roadmap** to a better professional environment in WST.
- An innovative **educational methodology** for highly-skilled and educated Water Sports Tourism professionals, who will act as local ambassadors and raise awareness about the preservation of the seas and oceans.
- A **Professional Qualification Framework** and the necessary mechanism for accreditation of the training centres and the certification of the Water Sports Tourism professionals.
- A complete **course on Water Sports Tourism** with five Training Modules focusing on a **Safety-First approach and inclusiveness in Water Sports**, including training people with disabilities. The course offers an online component and an On-the-Job Training, field component that is implemented as a summer training camp and leads to the certification of the Water Sports Tourism Professionals.
- An array of communication and dissemination actions, such as local and regional workshops, participation in conferences, networking events and career fairs, social media campaigns and publications.

Why a Co-design Workshop on Foresight?

Co-design foresight workshops can offer comprehensive and interactive insights into how a project or issue can develop. By involving multiple participants in the discussion, it enables an open exchange of ideas, allowing for a more thoughtful and holistic perspectives to be considered. These workshops can also help identify common goals and objectives and allow for the collective generation of innovative solutions and strategies.

The **co-design workshop on the future of Coastal Tourism jobs** took place in November 2022 in Athens and attracted approximately 27 participants from key stakeholders in coastal tourism. In this document we present **4 future scenarios for the coastal tourism as imagined and co-developed by participants**, during our workgroup. This report consolidates all findings, presents elaborated narratives for each scenario and refines the ideas that were discussed in the workshop.

Furthermore, we will explain the process that was followed in the design and the implementation of the workshop, the methodology that was used to engage participants and extract feedback, the steps we followed and the way we cross checked our assumptions and consolidated the group's feedback into a solid report. For reference purposes, since foresight is a relatively new practice (at least in these scientific fields) we have also provided a quick primer that will allow the reader to understand our approach and appreciate the insights.

2 What is Foresight?

Although we have already provided some explanation on foresight and why we are using it, a brief introduction to the science can be useful in better understanding the potential and its uses. This chapter provides exactly this: a very short introduction into foresight and its methodologies.

The forces of nature, social and political dynamics, scientific discovery, and technological innovation largely determine the future. However, as human capacity has evolved, our choices are also increasingly shaping the future. **Society cannot control the future, but it can influence the course of history.** This influence makes it worthwhile to analyze the trade-off between what is desirable and what is feasible.

To study the future is to study potential change - not simply fads, but what is likely to make a systemic or fundamental difference over the next 10 to 25 years or more. Studying the future is not simply economic projection or sociological analysis or technological forecasting, but a multi-disciplinary examination of change in all major areas of life to find the interacting dynamics that are creating the next age. (Glenn & Gordon, 2009)

In this context, foresight is a systematic, participatory, prospective, and policy-oriented process which, with the support of environmental and horizon scanning approaches, is aimed to actively engage key stakeholders into a wide range of activities anticipating, recommending and transforming technological, economic, environmental, political, social, and ethical futures (Georghiou L et al., 2009). In other words, Foresight is the knowledge or insight gained by studying future possibilities.

Figure 1: Forecast versus Foresight (Illustration by [Sebastian Buckup](#))

Key approaches to foresight include monitoring trends, developing forecasts and scenarios, checking assumptions and mental maps. Foresight involves taking a longer and broader view of

decision-making. Foresight enables organizations, agencies, and communities to more wisely create their futures and is often used to provide early warning of emerging issues, understand challenges and opportunities, clarify vision and goals, and check the appropriateness and robustness of strategies.

Megatrends

As mentioned above the concept of trends and megatrends are often used in foresight methodologies, and especially in scenarios. The terms and their characteristics are explained here in detail.

Trend (according to the Cambridge dictionary) is a **general development or change in a situation or in the way that people are behaving**. It is critical to understand that a trend is a long-term transformational process and not a short lived fad of the short that characterizes the clothing and FMCG (fast-moving consumer goods) industries. If an analogy with meteorology is used, trends would be climate changes rather than variations in the weather (Lindgren & Bandhold, 2003).

Figure 2: A typical trend development

The concept of **megatrend** was first introduced by John Naisbitt, in the book Megatrends (Naisbitt John, 1982). A **megatrend** is again a long-term transformational process, but with global reach, broad scope, and a fundamental dramatic impact. More specifically there are three dimensions that define a megatrend: time, reach, and impact (Vielmetter & Sell, 2014).

The Three Dimensions of a Megatrend

Figure 3: The three dimensions of a megatrend

Some of the main megatrends today are Urbanization, Climate Change, the rapid Technological developments (including Big Data, information technology, biotechnology, etc.), the growing demand for resources (food, water, and energy), the ageing global population, and the globally increasing middle class. Besides the established trends and megatrends, it is also important to check for weak signals of emerging trends (called *minitrends*) that promise to become significantly important within 2-5 years but are not yet generally recognized.

Trends, megatrends, and minitrends play an important role for composing future scenarios. Their development and cross-impacts are the steppingstones for building the alternative scenarios that illustrate plausible futures.

Scenarios & Scenario Planning

Scenario or scenarios in the context of foresight are consistent pictures, descriptions, stories illustrating future situations, future scenes. In other words, scenarios are alternative descriptions of different possible futures that help decision makers consider the implications of these future possibilities for planning and decision making today. Scenarios describing future situations are usually linked to the present in cause/effect logics. In other words, scenario is the coherent articulation of hypotheses for the evolution of variables in a given horizon and the road leading to it. However, there is no single definition of scenarios. Different practitioners have proposed different definitions:

- “An internally consistent view of what the future might turn out to be”(Porter Michael, 1985).
- “A tool [for] ordering one’s perceptions about alternative future environments in which one’s decision might be played out right” (Schwartz, 1991).
- “A disciplined method for imagining possible futures in which organizational decisions may be played out” (Schoemaker, 1995).

It is clear however, that a scenario is not a forecast, neither a vision. it is simply not possible to predict the future with certainty. A scenario is a well-worked answer to the question: “What can conceivably happen?” or “What would happen if ...?” (Lindgren & Bandhold, 2003). Scenarios are powerful tools that help us to perceive futures today. The scenarios challenge our mindsets and oblige us to consider a set of potentially uncomfortable futures.

The diagram illustrates the differences between the three main categories of futures. In general, the longer the time, the greater the possibilities for several different futures to occur. The number of possible one-week futures is limited, but the number of possible alternative futures in 30 years is enormous. By studying the different futures, some are preferable and more desirable, while some are more probable than others. However, the focus is further ahead, it becomes quite complex to predict the development of the system. Scenarios help put some order in this chaos.

Figure 4: The relations between possible, probable, and preferred futures.

Objective of Scenarios

The main purpose of using scenarios in foresight is to outline what the future might be – not will be – to show alternatives due to uncertainty, to make decision making more robust and future-proof, to sensitize decision makers with regard to the uncertainties of the future and to enable them to become future fit.

A scenario is never a prediction or a forecast, but a way of organizing many statements about the future; it is a plausible description of what might occur. Scenarios describe events and trends as they could evolve. Good scenarios are plausible, internally consistent and sufficiently interesting and exciting to make the future real enough to affect decision making.

Scenario Types

There is no consensus on the scenario typologies, however several typologies reflect the view that future studies explore possible, probable and/or preferable futures (Börjeson et al., 2006). Taken into account, this approach, we could define three (3) main scenario categories (See diagram). This classification of the scenarios is related with the structure and syntax of the focal question set by the scenario users. Scenario users can be those who generate scenarios, those who use already existing scenarios and those to whom scenarios are directed, even though they may not have asked for them. For example, different scenarios are produced by a “*What **will** happen?*” type of question, while also different category scenarios are produced by “*what **can** happen?*”, and “*How can a specific target be reached?*” types of questions.

Source: Börjeson *et al.* (in press, p. 3)

Figure 5: Three scenario categories, six scenario types

According to this approach the three main scenario categories are the following:

- **Predictive scenarios (What will happen?):** Predictive scenarios consist of two different types, distinguished by the conditions they place on what will happen. *Forecasts* respond to the question: What will happen, on the condition that the likely development unfolds? *What-if* scenarios respond to the question: What will happen, on the condition of some specified events?
The aim of predictive scenarios is to try to predict what is going to happen in the future. The concepts of probability and likelihood are closely related to predictive scenarios since trying to foresee what will happen in the future in one way or another must relate to the (subjectively) estimated likelihood of the outcome. Predictive scenarios are primarily drawn up to make it possible to plan and adapt to situations that are expected to occur. They are useful to planners and investors, who need to deal with foreseeable challenges and take advantage of foreseeable opportunities.
- **Explorative scenarios (What can happen?):** Explorative scenarios are distinguished between external and strategic and aim to explore situations or developments that are considered possible to happen. Typically, a set of scenarios is worked out to span a wide scope of possible developments.
Explorative scenarios resemble what-if scenarios, but the explorative scenarios are elaborated with a long time-horizon to explicitly allow for structural, and hence more profound, changes. Explorative scenarios can help explore developments that the intended target group in one way or another may have to take into consideration. This can be in situations when the structure to build scenarios around is unknown, e.g., in times of rapid and irregular changes.

There are two types of explorative scenarios. *External scenarios* focus only on factors beyond the control of relevant actors and are typically used from policy makers and planning entities for strategy development. The external scenarios can then help the user to develop robust strategies, i.e., strategies that will survive several kinds of external development. Policies are not part of the scenarios, but external scenarios provide a framework for the development and assessment of policies and strategies. One specific way of doing this is through *scenario planning*, a methodology described in section 1.4.3. On the other hand, *strategic scenarios* incorporate policy measures and aim to describe a range of possible consequences of strategic decisions.

- **Normative scenarios (How can a specific target be reached?):** In the case of normative scenarios, the study has explicitly normative starting points, and the focus of interest is on certain future situations or objectives and how these could be realised. Normative scenarios consist of two different types, distinguished by how the system structure is treated. Preserving scenarios respond to the question: How can the target be reached, by adjustments to the current situation? Transforming scenarios respond to the question: How can the target be reached, when the prevailing structure blocks necessary changes?
In normative preserving scenarios, the task is to find out how a certain target can be efficiently met. In transforming scenario studies, the starting point is a high-level and highly prioritised target, but this target seems to be unreachable if the ongoing development continues.

What next?

The whole idea of foresight is to get a better understanding of the future. But a better understanding without any action would mean nothing. The usefulness of foresight can be realised when we use it as our basis for designing a strategy for achieving our desired scenario and be better prepared for the undesired ones.

3 Thinking the Future: The Co-design Workshop

The Workshop's Aim

The aim of the Co-design workshop was to explore **the future of the coastal and nautical tourism in the Mediterranean area for the next 15-20 years.**

It was a highly interactive workshop where strategic foresight methods were used to explore innovative ideas and hopefully produce strategy proposals for the design and operation of new projects, activities, initiatives that could help the coastal tourism industry.

The target audience of the event were key stakeholders of coastal tourism sector including people from the industry, from educational institutions, from policy organisations and from societal actors. This amounted to 27 participants which were divided into 4 working groups.

The workshop started with a short introduction on foresight explaining the principles and defining the methodology that we would follow. A Co-design workshop needs a certain framework to avoid scope creep and keep the discussion within acceptable limits. This framework is defined by the workshop theme, objectives, assumptions, and code of conduct (how participants will work).

Workshop Scope & Objectives

The theme of a co-design workshop needs to be clearly and explicitly identified to avoid misconceptions and misunderstandings. It needs to provide the context and the environment. In our case we defined it as:

“Investigate the jobs, skills, and training that will be needed for the coastal tourism sector in 2040”.

Our objectives also need to be clearly defined. Foresight is gaining renewed attention, especially due to the uncertainty of our times and is recognised by EU as a very important tool (we give a primer on foresight and how we used it in the next chapter). The 3 objectives we selected for this exercise combined the future of coastal tourism in SE Mediterranean.

- Discuss challenges for innovation and competitiveness of the Coastal & nautical Tourism
- Explore changes in education and training curricula for highly skilled workforce in Coastal and Nautical Tourism
- Detect in a forward-looking methodology the new trends in the coastal and nautical tourism sector

Focal Question & Time Horizon

Every foresight exercise needs a focal question and a time horizon. In our exercise we used an 18-years horizon reaching to 2040. We tried to combine 2 questions:

- How the coastal and nautical tourism in the Mediterranean area could evolve by 2040?
- How developments will affect the job market, the required skills and the necessary training?

Using the methodology and the tools explained in the previous chapters, in this section we cover the qualitative analysis and our foresight insights. This chapter will provide our findings on:

- The **Environmental Scanning** and how workshop participants perceive their operating environment and the key stakeholders.
- The **Horizon Scanning** and the trends and uncertainties participants consider most crucial
- An **Impact Analysis** of the trends and uncertainties that will most certainly affect our scenarios
- A detailed narrative of the 4 **scenarios** taking as inputs the contributions from participants
- A consolidated **vision & mission** of the future IM System as seen through the innovative concepts and provocative ideas of the participants.

The vision for the future and policy recommendations are covered in the following and final chapter.

Tools & Methods

All the tools that were used were selected to provide the maximum interactivity and keep the audience involved as much as possible. We used a table setup in our venue with big round tables for 8 – 10 people. This allowed us to organise the whole group into 4 – 5 smaller teams. In each of these teams we had at least one member of the consortium to moderate the discussion and the process but not necessarily to act as a team leader. The teams quickly found their preferred way of working and collaborating and elected their representatives.

The Polak Game: How do you feel about the future?

We started the workshop with a quick game that forces participants to stand up and engage from the very first moment. The Polak Game was created by Dutch sociologist Fred Polak. In his work, “The Image of the Future,” he introduced this tool to test the view of the future of individuals (Polak & Boulding, 1973). The concept of Polak game is to use a 2X2 matrix with 2 axes:

- Optimistic/ Pessimistic (Do you believe things are getting better or worse in the longer run?)
- I can make a difference/ I can't make a difference (How capable are you to affect the future?)

In our exercise we created a yellow line in the floor of the room and asked participants to stand at a place across the 2 lines that they feel most confident by answering to the above questions. Depending on the answer, people will fall into one of the four categories as shown in the matrix below. This game of course does not produce definite or quantifiable results, but it gives an insight on how people view the future and their role in it.

Quick Insight: In our case most people felt optimistic for the future and believed that things are indeed getting better while at the same time most people believed they could influence the future and make a difference. This is a very positive and empowering insight.

Figure 6: The Polak game in action

Environmental Scanning

Identify the system – our contextual environment

Before we start thinking about the future and how this may evolve, we need to define our environment. Environmental scanning is more a background activity necessary in every foresight or co-design exercise. We need to “frame the system” we are going to investigate. In our case, we used one of the most established methodologies of environmental scanning. Environmental

scanning involves the systematic search for the forces of change in the environment which are considered largely outside of the control of the organization. We can divide the environment around us in three worlds:

- Contextual environment – Outer world: the world we cannot control
- **Operational environment – near world:** the world we can control to some (limited) extent
- **Inner world:** the world we control (= own organisation), the organisational, business or system itself

This can be better demonstrated in the following diagram, which was also used as the guidance template. To further facilitate investigation, we have defined 7+1 categories of events, influences, trends etc. These are: **Economy, Politics, Institutions, Social & Lifestyles, Technology & Science, Legal, Ecology & Health, Media**.

Participants were asked to identify all these forces and events and arrange them into the boards. This is a collaborative group exercise which facilitates interesting discussions on what really matters, and which players actually affect the future.

Figure 7: The outside-in perspective of a system or organisation

Figure 8: How an environmental scanning works. Participants use the template as a basis and add any item they feel it affects the system we are investigating.

Figure 9: The contextual environment of Coastal & Nautical Tourism as seen by our participants

The environmental scanning revealed no surprises. As expected, participants identified all major events that affected the industry. The recent geopolitical turmoil is also represented in the contextual map. Although not directly related with the sector, it is clear to all, that global financial problems and instability manifested through high inflation, the war in Europe, signs of recession in USA and continuous disruptions in global supply chains are still major factors of uncertainty and worries.

Looking back

Following the mapping of the contextual environment we asked participants to identify the major past events that had an effect in the sector and their impact may still reverberate. This exercise helps us reflect on past events and draw useful conclusions or assumptions for the future. The past matters because the better we can comprehend past trends, signals, events and their causes, the better assumptions and models we can build for exploring the future.

Taking a long historical view is important because it allows participant to discuss how the different events and developments have influenced our system and draw key connections. Such an exercise will help us to across the timeline:

- Think back: If we had known what would happen, how would we have acted differently?
- Think forward: How can history help us to understand and even shape the future?

To facilitate this exercise, we used a simple timeline starting 30-40 years back (or more if necessary, depending on our approach).

Figure 10: Exploring the past board

Quick Insight: participants quickly understood the exercise and defined all the institutions and players one would expect.

Figure 11: Past events in Greece and in the world that were significant for tourism

Since our target year is 2040, we started our timeframe about 40 years ago (1980). Undoubtedly, most of the events, especially those major global events are technological breakthroughs, political landmarks and financial earthquakes that shocked the world and redefined priorities. In the near world we tried to follow the evolution of the sectors with the various initiatives, regulations and priorities.

Standing out from this timeline are events like the introduction of Wind Surf as an Olympic Sport (1984), the launch of Web and site like booking.com (1990 – 1996), the establishment of low budget airlines (1995).

In events in our outer world, we can single out the Berlin Wall fall (1989), the financial crisis (2008), Brexit (2016) and of course COVID19 (2020) and of course the war that is menacing in Ukraine after Russia's attack.

Megatrend Analysis

Trends and Megatrends

As we have already defined our environment it is now time to look for the **drives of change**. The forces that will affect the future of our system and will initiate change. In this scanning exercise we are looking for trends and signals.

What is a trend?

According to Oxford Dictionary a trend is a general direction in which something is developing or changing. A fashion. In the context of foresight trends are **long-term changes in society**, in a certain direction. A trend is established and has a long-term impact. It is a driver and a force for change. In addition to trends, we also have the megatrends or global trends which are trends that have an effect in global scale.

Figure 12: Megatrends based on the analyses of forecasts coming from the WorldBank, WEF and a few Intelligence Agencies. (Saracco, 2020)

Why do we need trends and why do we start from them?

- Trends anchor us in reality – not in our fantasies, desires and hopes
- Trends focus on what is visible today – not what we want or hope to see in the future
- Trends reduce the risk that our “favorite themes” get too much attention
- Trends represent a more "objective" basis for discussion about the future, which usually lead to better conversations and more useful results

Before a trend is established and can be more easily identified, it is just a “**weak signal**”, an **uncertainty**. A weak signal is an indicator of a potentially emerging issue, that may become significant in the future. Weak signals supplement trend analysis and they can be used to expand on alternate futures. (Dufva, 2019).

Megatrend	Impact on your theme
Climate Change	-----
Resource scarcity	-----
Aging populations	-----
Global population growth	-----
Urbanization	-----
Rapid technological development	-----
Growing middle class globally	-----
Everything connected (Humans/Things)	-----
Volatile business environment	-----
Power shift to Asia	-----
Sustainability	-----

Figure 14: Analysing the impact of megatrends in our theme.

In this exercise we provided the Megatrend Analysis template (see Image). We asked participants to mark the strength of the impact of 10 megatrends on our theme (Drivers that will impact the Nautical and Coastal Tourism by 2040). Groups worked together, trying to define (in their opinion) and analyse the impact of megatrends on the Coastal Tourism Sector. This allowed us to identify even weak signals or outliers that are often hidden within a larger group. Our goal here was to see how much the already identified megatrends impact our theme. Are there any direct or indirect impacts? In the following diagram we can see a quick quantitative analysis of the results using both average and median values.

How important is the impact of the following megatrends on the future of Nautical and Coastal Tourism?

Figure 13: The impact of megatrends to our theme as voted by all participants through Menti.com

Not surprisingly, climate change and environmental degradation have the greatest influence on tourism, according to our participants. Technology advancement, resource scarcity, a volatile business environment, and a growing middle class round out the picture. So, let's have a look at the five most essential change agents:

- Climate Change and Environmental Degradation
- Rapid Technological Growth
- Resources Scarcity
- Volatile Business Environment
- Growing Middle Class

These megatrends are all well established and common in many similar exercises and their impact extends to all economic activities. These trends impact our theme through several factors:

Environmental Degradation

Figure 15: Image by Ken Hermann (<https://kenhermann.dk/>)

Global warming, energy crisis, extreme weather events, biodiversity loss, sea level rise, loss of coastal infrastructure, environmental degradation are all acknowledged as major problems and have one clear effect: the gradual destruction of our environment and a major economic impact on coastal businesses. Countries (especially in the less developed world) already experience clean

water and food shortages, forest fires, floods, loss of productive agricultural land, ocean pollution. All events that create a major impact in tourism.

Although we are, at last, experiencing a rise of **awareness** of the dangers and the declared will of governments and international organizations to act, it seems that our world is always behind, lacking the real interventions and investments that would have meaningful impact.

Nevertheless, in terms of impact in tourism, society now sees science, responsible behaviour as ethical spending and innovation and **research and innovation as the main drivers that could provide solutions**. A new generation, more environmentally responsible understands the dangers of ignoring climate change and pushes governments and international organization to take new initiatives and impose new regulations. It demands from businesses and industry to adopt environmentally responsible policies (ESG) and countries to shift to renewable energy sources.

Citizens demand better responses to immediate climate disaster crises and increased preparedness for the long term. Countries and International organisations are already working towards new regulations and initiatives that will at least mitigate the risks and stop the environmental destruction. In these declared initiatives, research and innovation will play a vital role with increased funding and public private partnerships that will allow mega projects.

Hot topics in this area (according to our group): Energy crisis, extreme weather events, seasonal changes, pollution, loss of coastal zone, Plastic Soup, environmental Degradation, change of beautiful beaches to landfills, sea level rise, loss of coastal infrastructure, etc. Research in these areas needs to be complemented with the necessary policies that will allow the quick adoption of these new technologies for the benefit of society.

Rapid Technological Development

Figure 16 : Photo by Robynne Hu on Unsplash

The pace of the development and adoption of new technologies is dramatically accelerating in the past decades. This rapid change is affecting every area of the economy, society and culture. (United Nations, 2019) The trend is clearly demonstrated by the transformation of analog into digital for every aspect of business, life, government. Rapid technological development highly affects global competition, with economies and countries that fall behind in technology lagging in other areas as well. A further impact of this trend is the continuous need for more and better trained personnel in new technologies and an increasing demand for tech savvy workers even at the lower levels of hierarchy that were previously outside of this purview.

On the other hand, technological development is lowering the costs of technologies allowing for further and wider adoption and creating new markets and users. The continuously lowering prices of new tourism services and the plethora of available and affordable tools for example, have been a major driver for an avalanche of new start-ups with new business models and services for both B2C & B2B and new innovative ideas and products. It was thanks to these changes that we see innovation appearing in the whole travel and tourism value chain, all around the world.

Hot topics in this area (according to our group): Digital Tourism, VR/AR, underwater tourism, new friendly tourism services, new trends apps services reviews share, Digital Nomads. In addition we may add Recycling and Energy related Technologies specifically for the hospitality sector, Artificial Intelligence. Technologies that will help solve societal problems (Social innovation) and create a better environment (recycling, green energy, health).

Resources Scarcity

Figure 17: Photo by Geetanjali Khanna on Unsplash

The scarcity of resources is often the aftermath of the environmental degradation and climate change, but it may also be a result of a geopolitical turmoil and shift from globalization to nationalism as the recent events with Russia's invasion to Ukraine and the subsequent sanctions can demonstrate. Overpopulation, excessive farming and fishing, pollution, and unsustainable lifestyles are all diminishing natural resources. When resources are few, competition becomes fiercer, resulting in local conflicts and even larger-scale warfare. It is the duty of science to respond to these challenges through R&I in circular economy, sustainable materials, recycling and reuse technologies, methods that will protect and preserve food sources and ensure access to clean water.

Hot topics in this area (according to our groups): Lack of Clean Water, Food, Increased Costs, Services adaptation, Biodiversity loss, Capacity reduction, Energy, Water quality. We may add: Research into new materials and methods to increase the productivity and to decrease dependency on specific unsafe and limited resources. Adoption of new clean fuels like hydrogen, optimized use of scarce resources, sustainability and lifecycle control or products, addressing health inequalities due to resource scarcity.

Volatile Business Environment

If the recent financial and geopolitical crises have taught us anything, it is that global uncertainty is increasing. Economies become more and more volatile and the model upon which the West was based is under scrutiny if not direct attack. The aftermath of COVID19, the disruption of value chains, a persistent inflation in Europe and USA, abnormally high for the standards of these economic areas and possibility of new recession in EU are all causes for concern and factors that will heavily impact coastal tourism. A continuous economic volatility will complicate policy decisions, forcing governments to focus on more pressing measures often at the expense of all other productive sectors.

Hot topics in this area (according to our group): Digital Nomads, Teleworking, Human Central management style, risk mitigation, high investments risks hesitation, last minute planning, lower demand, seasonality, insecurity, loss of interest to work in the field.

Growing Middle Class

Figure 18: Photo by [Jack Finnigan](#) on [Unsplash](#)

The growth of the middle class is having a significant impact on the tourism industry. With more disposable income, the middle class is able to afford more leisure activities and travel; as a result, there is an increase in the demand for tourism. Tour operators have had to adapt their offerings to meet the needs of the growing middle class, such as creating more affordable and accessible trips, and providing more unique experiences. This has led to more people travelling, and an increase in tourism spending.

The growth of the middle class also means that businesses in the tourism sector have had to expand their target audience to include a wider demographic. This has allowed tourism businesses to increase their customer base and create more personalised experiences, which in turn has led to an increase in revenue. Additionally, it has enabled businesses to build better relationships with their customers and create a more loyal customer base. All of this has resulted in a boost to the tourism industry.

However, this uptick in tourism spending may lead to an increase in demand for tourist goods and services, which can be difficult for the industry to keep up with. The tourism industry must be agile and quick to adapt to their new audience. It is also likely that they will need to invest in new marketing techniques and campaigns in order to keep up with the changing market.

Drivers of Change

The second template was used in the group work, where all participants had to classify the trends and uncertainties they saw, under the categories defined in our environmental scanning: **Politics, Economy & Companies, Society & Individual, Technology & Innovation, Legal Environment.**

Once the trends and uncertainties were identified and analysed by our groups it was time to consolidate our findings and bring everything together. Groups were called to **select one trend and one uncertainty per category (PESTLE)** and add it to a new **Drivers of Change board**. This allowed a first filtering of the most important notions and a new board where each group contributed equally.

Figure 19: Identifying the drivers of change. The trends and the weak signals.

Figure 20: One of the actual boards used in the exercise.

The codification and consolidation of the results of the “Drivers of Change” boards, was the next step in the analysis of the trends and uncertainties. Following the same approach as before we used the PESTLE framework, which allows us to better organize our findings into 6 categories:

POLITICS	ECONOMY	SOCIETY	TECHNOLOGY	LEGAL	ENVIRONMENT
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Although these categories clearly overlap, their use gives an easy way to group trends into broad categories. As a result, the table below has been streamlined and compacted to provide interesting insights and a sneak peek at the wider picture.

POLITICS	ECONOMY	SOCIETY	TECHNOLOGY	LEGAL	ENVIRONMENT
STRONG TRENDS					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Populism, Inequalities • EU Green Deal • Coastal Planning, • Policy Changes, • Regional Governance • Identity Politics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Life Centric Focus (ESG) • SMEs Buyouts • Transport Connectivity • Funding Policies • Mega Projects, • Green Business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical Spending • Activity based holidays • Endangered Local Rural Identities • Energy Crisis • Education/ VET • Societal Impact awareness • Increased Inequality • Sustainable behaviors • Connect with locals • Connect to nature • Digital Nomads 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NEW activities • Electric Vehicles • Space Tourism • Metaverse changes customer experience • Underwater robotics exploration • VR/AR • Renewable energy techs • Decarbonization of shipping • Biofuel development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common Legal Frameworks • Pandemic Related Regulation • Environmental Protection Legislation • Managed Service Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustainability Guidelines • Most Frequent Pandemics • Dangerous, Invasive Species • Marine Pollution • Sea level Rise • Climate Change • Plastic Soup • Circular economy • Eco Museum •
WEAK SIGNALS					
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bottom-up Movements, • Polarisation of conflict, • Sanctions • Limited access to destinations • World Tourist Visa • Conflicts • South MED countries • Local Sustainability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visitors' Regulations drive innovation • New business models • Diversification of tourism (Pesca-Tourism) • Offshore Companies • Local Companies as leaders • Hydroplanes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Behavioral Change • Seeking fast experiences • New Generation mission • Simple natural experiences the new luxury • Surveillance fears • Independent tourists • lack of Skills • Cruise tourism • Slow tourism • Quality life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Material Science Innovation for waste reductions • Change of film industry • Global Tourists credits system • Hydrogen Energy • VR Tourism • Digitalisation and Services • Autonomous shipping • Wind Energy in passenger ships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health Passport • Rights of the earth • Secure horizontal framework (safety, quality, training) • Unconventional types - forms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transition from Human Centric to Life Centric • Protected areas accessible to high end tourism • Water Toxicity • Dangerous Materials • Natural hazards • Infrastructure challenges • Natura • Ecosystem Services Quality • Ancient Viruses

It should be noted that in the above table the drivers are presented randomly as they appeared in the boards. They are very useful in presenting sentiments and spark discussions but cannot be used in any

quantitative way. The word cloud below however, may provide an idea of which weak signal or uncertainty participants consider more important.

The Thing from the Future

The Thing from The Future is an **award-winning imagination game** that challenges players to describe objects collaboratively and competitively from a range of alternative futures. The game was designed by the Situation Lab and has been used around the world in different ways. There is great flexibility in the game's uses – from group icebreaker to imagination gym, tool for structured exploration of a design space or as engine for tangible outcomes.

*We decided to use the game in our workshop as an engaging creative exercise before **we continue** with the development of the scenarios. The game provided an excellent opportunity for participants to think outside the box. Reflect on the future and visualise possible solutions to future problems.*

The game is simple and quite enjoyable. The object of the game is to come up with the most entertaining and thought-provoking descriptions of hypothetical objects from different near-, medium-, and long-term futures. Each round, players collectively generate a creative prompt by playing a card game. This prompt outlines the kind of future that the **thing-to-be-imagined** comes from, specifies what part of society or culture it belongs to, describes the type of object that it is, and suggests an emotional reaction that it might spark in an observer from the present. Players must then each write a short description of an object that fits the constraints of the prompt. These descriptions are then read aloud (without attribution), and players vote on which description they find the most interesting, provocative, or funny. The winner of each round keeps the cards put into play for that round, and whoever has the most cards when the game ends is declared the overall winner. (Gandy & Watson, 2014) The game provides 4 types of cards:

- **Prompts** (possible futures): Grow, Collapse, Discipline and Transform
- **Terrain cards** describe contexts, places, and topic areas.
- **Object cards** describe the basic form of the thing from the future.
- **Mood cards** describe emotions that the thing from the future might evoke in an observer from the present.

Figure 22: The player is picking 4 cards: The ARC defines the future. The Terrain card the theme or the area, the object card asks defines the object we want to work on, and the mood defines how a future user may feel.

Using the above deck as an example: players must come up with ideas for a postcard from 30 years in the future, in a world where continued growth is the defining characteristic. The postcard should somehow reflect the Terrain (theme, context) of Education, and the Mood that the object might evoke in an observer should be one of excitement.

Figure 23: The template that was used to facilitate the work.

The game proved an excellent opportunity for creative, out of the box thinking. All groups grasped the idea and produced very interesting proposals for future objects, both tangible and intangible. The purpose of the game was not to elaborate the trends and uncertainties that were identified in the previous exercises, but rather to engage participants in creative thinking that would prepare them for the next exercises of scenarios building and strategy ideas.

4 Scenarios: The future Coastal and Nautical Tourism

Scenario Building & Strategy Ideas

Before we go deeper in the analysis of our findings and the presentation of the scenarios, it is worth remembering our focal question. The focal question provides the necessary guidance for our investigation. It helps us restrict our assumptions and research to a specific timeframe and area. In our case we combined 2 interconnected focal questions that are also heavily interdependent. We used these questions because we wanted to explore how key stakeholders envision the future of coastal tourism and how the jobs and skills market will be affected.

- How the coastal and nautical tourism in the Mediterranean area could evolve by 2040?
- How developments will affect the job market, the required skills and the necessary training?

The development of scenarios for the future is the main task of a foresight exercise. A scenario is a **vision of a possible future** described in a clear and intuitive way. It is based on the trends and the uncertainties we have identified, and it is the culmination of the foresight process. Scenarios are not predictions of the future but rather descriptions of possible futures. This is why we describe not just one but 4 or even more scenarios based on our key findings. This exercise processes the findings of the previous analysis of the trends and uncertainties that our focus group collectively defined. This is why the contributions and the findings of the group of our participants are so important: they provide us with the guidelines for our scenario building.

It is important to remember that scenarios are just representative narratives of the future. They are not predictions, policy, or plans. They represent perspectives, hypothesis, expectations, and assumptions. (UNDP, 2018) The scenarios can and should be used as the basis for a further understanding of the driving forces of society and our organisation and as a starting point for developing an appropriate strategy and the relevant policies.

Dator's Laws of the Future

The Future cannot be predicted because the future does not exist.

Any useful idea about the futures should appear to be ridiculous.

We shape out tools and thereafter our tools shape us.

In building our scenarios we used the 4 archetypes method (or 4 generic futures), originally developed by Jim Dator at the University of Hawaii at Mānoa (Dator, 2009). Dator's 4 Archetypes Method is a strategic foresight tool used to create meaningful and forward-thinking scenarios.

This method was developed by futurist and foresight expert Jim Dator and consists of four steps: 1) Discovery, 2) Selection and Assessment, 3) Imagination, and 4) Implementation.

Figure 24: Dator's 4 Futures

The Discovery step involves researching and analyzing the current environment, potential drivers of change, and possible trends. This includes researching the latest trends, market conditions, technology advances, and other relevant data points. Through this step, the team identifies possible opportunities, threats, and trends that might affect their organization.

The Selection and Assessment step involves evaluating the discovered data and selecting the most relevant data points. By prioritizing the information, the team can focus on the topics that are most likely to have a significant impact, both positive and negative.

The Imagination step involves creating potential scenarios and exploring their implications. The team uses their research and creative thinking to develop scenarios that might occur in the future and how the organization should respond to them.

The Implementation step involves creating plans to prepare for the scenarios identified during the Imagination step. At this stage, the team develops strategies to help the organization prepare for the future, such as developing plans for new products or services, adjusting existing products and services, or exploring new opportunities.

To facilitate work in groups we assigned the development of one scenario to each group. Since we had 4 groups, we ended up with 4 full scenarios. The groups received a board which they could use to elaborate the scenario narrative and suggest some strategy. At the end of the session, each group presented its scenario findings, and all scenarios were demonstrated so that all groups could see and discuss them.

Our scenaria building exercise was paired with a Live-in Scenario exercise where participants had to envision 3 start-ups that would operate in such a future.

Figure 25: Scenario Building and Live-in Scenario boards

Participants had to create 3 future tourism startups thinking about their products and services, their customers and the skills/training that would be necessary work in them. At the end of the exercise, each group pitched their ideas to all participants with the goal to attract funding.

In the following pages we present a detailed narrative of the 4 scenarios based solely on the ideas and suggestions of the participating groups. Remember however that scenarios are not predictions. They can be a very useful learning and strategy tool that can help us to better prepare for the forthcoming changes.

The four scenarios that we describe are all set at 2040 and are based on our underlying analysis of the trends and uncertainties:

<p>2: Growth WHALE</p>	
<p>3: Transformation CORAL REEF</p>	

Scenario 1 [COLLAPSE]: SEA WORM

FUTURE	COLLAPSE	DRIVERS	ENVIRONMENTAL CRISIS, ETHICS, ENERGY		
POLITICS	ECONOMY	SOCIETY	TECH & INNOVATION	LEGAL	ENVIRONMENT
World War III Conflicts	Anarchy, Side Economy, Self- Regulation, Corporate Piracy	Deaths, Nomadic Communities	Downgrade, Internet/ social media, Communication breakdown	Rule of Law collapse, Vigilante	Renewable Energy cannot cover needs, Microplastics, Toxicity, Radiation, Sea food resources reduction

It has been nearly 10 years since the world saw the catastrophic effects of World War III. In the aftermath of the war, the global landscape has drastically changed. Governments have become more authoritarian and side economies have emerged. Anarchy and corporate piracy have become the norm in many parts of the world. The world has become more insecure, with many areas experiencing continuous energy shortages, environmental disasters, a breakdown in rule of law and communication breakdowns. The emergence of vigilante groups, gangs, and nomadic communities has further complicated the situation.

Coastal tourism has been one of the worst affected industries. Once a thriving industry, it has been greatly impacted by the conflicts and environmental degradation that ensued. A lot of coastal areas have been drastically downgraded due to the destruction of infrastructure, the lack of access to renewable energy sources, and the presence of microplastics and other toxins in the water. The sea food resources have been reduced due to radiation from the war and contamination from pollutants.

Despite the collapse, tourism still exists, and new destinations have emerged in survived coastal communities. Many tourists now prefer to explore these communities, rather than traditional tourist hotspots. A lot of these communities are fast becoming top destinations for coastal tourism, where the situation is much better than the rest of the world. This trend has led to the growth of a side, mostly local, economy, where individuals can make a living by catering to the needs of these tourists. Social media and internet communications are all but gone, replaced by localised information networks that ran on renewable energy.

Renewable energy sources cannot cover the needs of the industry and cities, but at a local level they do provide an adequate level of energy autonomy in these communities. It is clear that the future of coastal tourism is far from bright, but it is not without hope. The situation may seem bleak, but some progress is being made. Scientists are working tirelessly to address the environmental challenges that we face, and self-regulation is becoming more effective. However, it will take time and concerted effort from all members of society to rebuild and create a better future for ourselves and the planet.

Scenario 2 [GROWTH]: WHALE

FUTURE	CONTINUED GROWTH	DRIVERS	TECHNOLOGY ADVANCEMENT, WORLD STABILITY (ECONOMIC, PEACE), CLIMATE CHANGE		
 ENVIRONMENT					
Environmental Protection, Border Controls, EU Green Deal	Alternative Tourism, Upskilling	Local Vore (eating local), Floating cities, Luxury yachting, Mega Super Yachts	Sustainable Transport (Drones), Renewable Energy Sources	EU Green Deal	Renewable Energy

In the year 2040, coastal tourism has become a completely different scene than it was just decades prior. With the multitude of technology advancements, world stability, and climate change, the world has undergone a dramatic transformation in how it views coastal tourism.

Environmental protection has become of paramount importance, as governments around the world have worked to put into action legislation to protect their coastal coastlines from the damage of increasing tourism. Border controls have been tightened, with only the most knowledgeable travelers being allowed entry to the most popular destinations.

The EU Green Deal has provided a policy framework to support the growth of local tourism businesses, providing incentives to businesses to invest in sustainable and renewable energy sources. Alternative tourism, such as floating cities and luxury yachting, have become increasingly popular as a way to explore the coastal areas without directly harming the environment.

Upskilling of local populations has become essential in helping to provide the necessary knowledge and infrastructure to support coastal tourism in the future. Local-vore (eating only locally-grown foods) is becoming increasingly popular as tourists look to experience the local delicacies and culture of the destination.

Renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and geothermal have become the norm in powering the floating cities, and sustainable transport such as the use of drones has become a viable option for getting around coastal destinations.

In the future of coastal tourism, sustainability and environmental protection will be the driving force of the industry, and the necessary steps taken to ensure a safe and enjoyable experience for all will be of paramount importance.

Scenario 3 [DISCIPLINE]: OYSTER

FUTURE	DISCIPLINE	DRIVERS	FEAR OF CHANGE, NEED FOR COLLABORATION, RESOURCES SCARCITY		
POLITICS	ECONOMY	SOCIETY	TECH & INNOVATION	LEGAL	ENVIRONMENT
Further EU expansion, EU of 2 gears, Large scale conflict, nuclear destruction	Mediation companies boom, EU economic collapse	Polarization, Introversion, New pandemic COVID30, Teleworking	Lawful interception technologies, telecoms tracking technology control technology	Territorial dispute government regulation on controlling energy, water, raw resources use	Invasive species, extreme weather events (Tsunami, fires, tornados)

In 2040, coastal tourism is in a very different state than it was just a few years ago. The world has stabilized and is in a disciplined period, driven by fear of change and the need for collaboration. Resources are scarce, and this has caused a further expansion of the European Union, resulting in a two-gear system with different levels of economic growth.

Large scale conflict has become a thing of the past, and nuclear destruction is increasingly rare. This new period of relative peace has caused the growth of mediation companies, which have made negotiations between international organizations and governments much smoother.

At the same time, the EU has experienced an economic collapse, leading to political polarization and introversion. The new pandemic, COVID30, has brought about even more stringent restrictions on movement, and teleworking has become the norm.

Lawful interception technologies, telecoms, tracking technology and control technology have been used to keep track of people and resources, and control energy, water and raw resource use. Territorial disputes have resulted in government regulations on controlling energy, water, raw resources use, and invasive species.

Due to extreme weather events, such as tsunamis, fires and tornados, coastal tourism has had to adapt. Governments have restricted access to some areas and have implemented more stringent safety guidelines. The industry has become more reliant on technology, with the use of virtual reality, drones and automated systems for tracking and surveillance.

Overall, coastal tourism has been drastically changed due to the events of the past twenty years. It has become more regulated, more technological, and more focused on safety. But despite the changes, it is still a major global industry, providing a much-needed source of income in many countries.

Scenario 4 [TRANSFORMATION]: CORAL REEF

FUTURE	TRANSFORMATION	DRIVERS	CLIMATE CHANGE, BIODIVERSITY, CHANGE OF VALUES, ETHICS, POPULATION, DEMOGRAPHIC SHIFT		
POLITICS	ECONOMY	SOCIETY	TECH & INNOVATION	LEGAL	ENVIRONMENT
EU Green Deal, Blue Deal, Integration policies, SDGs all met, Demilitarization	Redefining corporate values, ESG, Budget allocation to environment, World Regulated Currency	Ethical Spending, Consumer behavior, education (Green, Blue) mRNA Vaccines for everything	Plastic Alternative, Booming material science, renewables rule	Strict Legal Framework for managing waste, Rights of non-human beings, Nuclear Weapons banned, Cryptocurrencies banned	Net zero goals met, China-USA sign full agreement

In 2040, coastal tourism has undergone a dramatic transformation. Climate change has forced many popular tourist destinations to completely re-examine the way they operate and the services they offer. In order to adapt to these changes, many countries have implemented EU Green and Blue Deals, as well as an integration of policies to ensure sustainability and environmental protection.

The world has seen the successful achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals, creating a more equitable society for all. This is largely due to demilitarization, the redefinition of corporate values, and the emergence of ESG investing. Moreover, budgets allocated to the environment have been dramatically increased, allowing for the restoration of natural habitats.

The global economy is now regulated with a single world currency and ethical spending is more and more commonplace. Meanwhile, consumer behaviour has become increasingly more conscious and environmentally friendly, leading to a significant drop in the production of single-use plastic. In addition, the booming field of material science has provided many innovative alternatives to plastic and other environmentally damaging solutions.

The world has largely moved away from traditional energy sources and renewables now rule the power market. Additionally, a strict legal framework has been established to manage waste and protect the environment, while granting non-human beings certain rights. Nuclear weapons have been banned, while cryptocurrencies have been outlawed to protect the world's economy. Finally, the world has achieved its goal of reaching net zero emissions, while China and the United States have signed a full agreement to ensure continued collaboration in the fight against climate change. Coastal tourism has adapted to this new world and has become a much more sustainable and responsible industry. With countries investing heavily in education and new technologies, coastal tourism has the potential to become an increasingly popular activity that benefits both the environment and the local communities.

5 The Vision of the future: building Start-ups

Live-in Scenarios

Scenarios are an effective technique to examine future possibilities since they foster creative and critical thinking. Each scenario reflects a unique perspective on the future, ranging from unexpected developments to bold aspirations for extreme change. Participants are able to think proactively and constructively about the future of coastal tourism by analyzing the various options. In our workshop participants were encouraged to explore the ramifications of their scenarios for the tourism sector and to come up with three startup concepts for each scenario. This activity assists us in developing a comprehensive vision of the future and frequently offers surprising ideas that challenge our expectations and prompt us to think more imaginatively about our future strategies.

Figure 26: Live-in Scenarios Preparation and Pitching

Our participants not only developed the concept of 12 new startups suitable for the future they imagined, but they also pitched their ideas to the entire group. We employed dot-voting or dotmocracy to quantify our findings in a more interesting way. Dotmocracy is a proven facilitation approach for describing voting with dot stickers or marker pen marks. (Dotmocracy, n.d.) The following steps were included in the procedure:

- Dot stickers were distributed to each participant (stars). Each star symbolized a 100K €.
- They were instructed to "invest" these funds in the startup concept they liked most.

This quantification assisted us in measuring the opinion and reaction to each of the concepts, and it was also a very entertaining way to conclude the session

The Startups

	SEA WORM Startups – The world has collapsed			WHALE Startups – Growth and prosperity		
	TAMADES	ADES	DINEUNDER	SUPER SEAGAL	SUPER TURTLE	SUPER ALGAE TOURISM
Description	Tailor-made After-death Experiences	Underworld Resorts	Food Supplier, Underground Worm Farm (Food Security)	Drone transportation Uber-like service	Floating and underwater accommodation	Agua Agrotourism
Product / Service	Experiences	Accommodation, Development, Real Estate Development	Agri-Food	Customised, personal transportation (efficient, sustainable, and affordable)	Floating and submersible autonomous villas (cruise on/under water)	Harvest aquatic seafood.
Customers	Everyone, high-end tourists	Society, Tourists, Constructors, Investors	Producers, Farmers, Delivery Boys, Communities	Tourists and Travellers	All meritime costal dwellers	Adventurous, eco-conscious tourists
Skills / Training	Research / Designers, Promotion, sales, Onsite Implementation	Engineering, Construction, Sales, Tourism Education	Production, Processing, logistics, Sales, Communication, Marketing	Drone development operations and maintenance	Underwater engineering design, development	Scuba-diving
Funding collected	€ 1.200.000	€ 700.000	€ 800.000	€ 800.000	€ 1.800.000	€ 900.000

	OYSTER Startups – The world is disciplined			CORAL REEF Startups – We are under transformation		
	BlueClean	DeedView	Gelly Fish Wash	Weaponize	De-Bias	The Blue Way
Description	Ocean/Sea clean-up and recycling of waste material	Low-cost surface/deep sea tourism	Gelly fish recycling	Military Equipment Recycling	Consultancy for behavioural change	Blue Energy Harvesting
Product / Service	Ocean and Sea treatment (Polluters pay service)	Tourism Experiences	Collection of excess population of gelly fish	Decommissioned military equipment for: underwater diving parks, consumables, for hospitality, base facilities turn into theme parks	Develop educational material for Green Transition, Incentives for states and organisations, Gamification for transition behaviour	Plan and develop equipment to harvest energy from sea and costal activities, design entertaining experiences
Customers	Governmental body, Polluters (big shipping companies, plastics industry)	Tourist agents, individual tourists, education bodies, R&D bodies, Coast guard, authorities	Cosmetics, food companies, fertiliser companies	Countries, states, governments, Hospitality Sector, Enterprises, individuals B2B, B2C	Multinationals, tourism sector companies, individuals/ households	Water, Coastal, Sea activities centre, hotels, hospitality, individual
Skills / Training	Environmental Studies, engineers, material science, sea observation	oceanography, archaeology, IT, Soft Skills / Communication	biology, chemistry, biotechnology	Divers, technical skills, soft skills creativity, adaptability	Diverse, psychometrics, change management, creativity, soft skills	Diverse, engineers, soft skills, management
Funding collected	€ 1.200.000,00	€ 2.000.000,00	€ 1.100.000,00	€ 1.300.000	€ 300.000	€ 1.000.000

And the winner is DeepView.

6 What now? The next steps

This co-design workshop was not originally planned as a deliverable. However, we believe that such an exercise is the finest method to investigate the past and plan for the future. It was a participative event, which participants appreciated and actively participated in.

Foresight co-design workshops are a fantastic method to uncover challenges, explore issues, and envisage future solutions. The outcomes of this workshop clearly show that tourism has a future even in the worst-case scenario.

The workshop's outcomes will be useful in developing our long-term strategy. They will enable us to develop a better vision and mission for the future, as well as a strategy for achieving it.

We hope that the report will be a valuable resource not only for our project's partners, but also for the coastal community as a whole.

7 References

- Börjeson, L., Höjer, M., Dreborg, K. H., Ekvall, T., & Finnveden, G. (2006). Scenario types and techniques: Towards a user's guide. *Futures*, 38(7).
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2005.12.002>
- Dator, J. (2009). Alternative futures at the Manoa School. *Journal of Futures Studies*, 14(2).
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-07809-0_5
- Dufva, M. (2019, January 19). *What is a weak signal?* SITRA.
<https://www.sitra.fi/en/articles/what-is-a-weak-signal/>
- Gandy, S., & Watson, J. (2014). *The thing from the future*. Situation Lab.
<http://situationlab.org/project/the-thing-from-the-future/>
- Georghiou L, Harper JC, Keenan M, Miles I, & Popper R. (2009). The Handbook of Technology Foresight. *Foresight*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1108/14636680910936486>
- Glenn, J. C., & Gordon, T. J. (2009). Futures Research Methodology, Version 1.0. *Millennium Project*.
- Lindgren, M., & Bandhold, H. (2003). Scenario Planning: An Introductory Overview. In *Scenario Planning*. https://doi.org/10.1057/9780230511620_3
- Naisbitt John. (1982). *Megatrends: Ten New Directions Transforming Our Lives*. Grand Central Pub.
- Polak, F., & Boulding, E. (1973). The Image of the Future. In *American Journal of Sociology*. Elsevier Scientific Publishing.
- Porter Michael, E. (1985). Competitive Advantage: Creating and sustaining superior performance. *The Free*.
- Saracco, R. (2020, November 14). Megatrends for this decade. *IEE Future Directions*.
<https://cmte.ieee.org/futuredirections/2020/11/14/megatrends-for-this-decade-i/>
- Schoemaker, P. J. H. (1995). Scenario planning: a tool for strategic thinking ? *Sloan Management Review* 36 (2), 25–40 (Winter 1995). *Sloan Management Review*, 36(3).
- Schwartz, P. (1991). Creating Scenario Building Blocks. In *The Art of the Long View: Paths to Strategic Insight for Yourself and Your Company*.
- UNDP. (2018). *Foresight Manual: Empowered Futures for the 2030 Agenda*.
- United Nations. (2019). *The impact of rapid technological change on sustainable development*.
- Vielmetter, G., & Sell, Y. (2014). Leadership 2030. In *Leadership 2030: The Six Megatrends You Need to Understand to Lead Your Company into the Future*.